
110. Variation of the gravitational constant

DO THE FUNDAMENTAL physical constants vary with time? I will set this important topic in a wider context, then focus on methods that can place limits on a possible time-variation of the gravitational constant, G , and specifically on areas where Gaia might contribute.

But let me be clear: apart from an improved proper motion for the white dwarf G117–B15A, Gaia has made little explicit contributions to this question... so far!

A FUNDAMENTAL PHYSICAL CONSTANT is one considered to be universal in nature, and constant in time. The term can also refer to *dimensionless* physical constants, e.g. the fine-structure constant (α). And note that the choice of ‘defining constants’ in the SI system is a somewhat separate question (Tiesinga et al., 2021).

The number of fundamental constants depends on the theoretical framework. Today, our best description of Nature is governed by two distinct theories: general relativity (for gravity) and the ‘Standard Model’ (for the electromagnetic, weak and strong nuclear interactions).

Together these result in a total of 19 fundamental constants (e.g. Uzan 2011). Amongst them are the gravitational constant (G), the speed of light (c), and the Planck constant (h), with all 16 others from the Standard Model (Yukawa couplings, Higgs field, and others).

That our description of the physical world remains incomplete is signalled by the absence of a quantum theory of gravity, and by the challenges in explaining dark matter and dark energy, baryon (matter/anti-matter) asymmetry, the strong CP problem, and others.

FUNDAMENTAL CONSTANTS are not predicted by theory, but can only be determined by measurement. Accordingly, much effort is being invested in quantifying their possible rates of change, with the goal of confirming (or invalidating) the associated theory.

Several methods can probe the *non-gravitational* constants, i.e. assuming that $\alpha_G = Gm_p^2/\hbar c$ is constant (α_G appears in Dirac’s large number hypothesis). Various complications, or further assumptions, are required for the interpretation of all of these methods (e.g. Uzan 2021), and I will give only a concise listing for context.

In increasing order of ‘look-back time’, these use: (a) laboratory measurements of the relative frequencies of atomic transitions; (b) isotopes from the Oklo (Gabon) natural ^{235}U reactor 1.8 Gyr ago; (c) long-lived α - or β -decay isotopes in ancient meteorites; (d) time variation of the fine-structure constant from quasar doublet lines; (e) nuclear reactions necessary for the observed stellar production of carbon; (f) others based on the cosmological model (including use of the 21 cm H-line, the cosmic microwave background, and light element abundances).

TURNING TO the gravitational constant: according to general relativity, and specifically as a consequence of the equivalence principle, G is constant.

The latest numerical value adopted by CODATA 2018 is $6.67430(15) \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$. Its large relative standard uncertainty, 2.2×10^{-5} , in part explains the relatively weak constraints on a possible time variation.

The possibility of the variation of G over cosmological time has been debated since it was introduced by Milne (1935) as a consequence of an alternative to general relativity, and by Weyl (1919), Eddington (1931), Dirac (1937), Jordan (1947), and recently Valev (2021), in their considerations of the ‘**large numbers hypothesis**’, relating coincidences between certain very large dimensionless numbers characterising the Universe.

OBSERVATIONAL CONSTRAINTS ON \dot{G} have come from three main classes of experiment:

- (a) solar system observations, including the Moon’s orbit, radar timing to Venus and Mercury, and ranging of the Mariner 10 and Viking spacecraft.
- (b) pulsar timing: monitoring of the spin down of binary pulsars (PSR B1913+16 and PSR B1855+09), as well as a few isolated pulsars (notably PSR J0437–4715).
- (c) constraints from stellar evolution, specifically based on helioseismology, the ages of globular clusters, white dwarf cooling, and Type II supernovae.

It is this final category where Gaia can be expected to contribute, and where I will go into a little more detail in the following.

THE REASON why star observations can be used to place limits on any variation of G is straightforward in principle, and first outlined by physicists Edward Teller (1948) and George Gamow (1967).

The rate of photon energy escape from a star is limited by its surface opacity. In the simplistic case of opacity dominated by Thomson scattering, the stellar luminosity is given by $L \propto G^4 M^3$, and the main sequence lifetime is consequently highly sensitive to the value of G . Indeed, as shown by Uzan (2003), under the Dirac hypothesis, the nuclear fuel of the Sun would already have been exhausted!

Degl'Innocenti et al. (1996) used stellar evolutionary models to show that low-mass stars in globular clusters evolving from the zero age main sequence to the red giant branch more accurately satisfy $L \propto G^{5.6} M^{4.7}$. Their fitting to the main sequence turnoff, on the assumption of a linear variation of G with time, gave the constraint $-35 \times 10^{-12} < \dot{G}/G < 7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, with the positive upper limit implying that gravity was weaker in the past.

Constraints from the Sun come from evolutionary models constrained by its initial helium abundance, combined with measured p-mode frequencies from helioseismology. These agree well with standard predictions, particularly when including the gravitational settling of He, leaving little scope for the helium interior to differ substantially from standard models, and providing independent constraints on \dot{G} (Demarque et al. 1994).

THE LARGEST EFFECTS of a time-varying gravitational constant might be expected for the oldest stellar objects, which is why white dwarfs are important in this context (Isern et al., 2022). And there are two aspects of relevance to Gaia: the white dwarf luminosity function, and pulsation variations in individual objects.

The faintest white dwarfs formed shortly after the birth of the Galactic disk, and their late evolution is dominated by cooling and gravitational contraction under hydrostatic equilibrium. Accordingly, any change in G modifies their energy balance, which in turn modifies their luminosity.

In consequence, the age of the disk, which can be estimated from the rapid drop at the faint end of the white dwarf luminosity function, depends on the value of G in the past (Vila, 1976). This approach was used by García-Berro et al. (1995) to derive an upper bound of $\dot{G}/G \leq -(1 \pm 1) \times 10^{-11} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, further reduced to $\dot{G}/G \leq -1.8 \times 10^{-12} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ by García-Berro et al. (2011).

Improved knowledge of the white dwarf luminosity function from Gaia, combined with an independent age of the disk in the solar neighbourhood, should translate into an even more stringent upper bound.

These limits can be compared with the most stringent from stellar evolution, being $\dot{G}/G \leq 2 \times 10^{-13} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ from helioseismology (Bonanno & Fröhlich, 2020)

THE SECOND AREA where white dwarfs are contributing to the limits on \dot{G} concerns their pulsation properties. Again, a secular variation of the gravitational constant would modify their structure and evolutionary time scales, resulting in a change in their pulsation periods. Details differ according to spectral subtype, ranging from the H-dominated DAV (ZZ Ceti) stars, the He-dominated DBV (V777 Her) stars, to the hottest DOV (GW Vir) stars (Isern et al., 2022, §5).

The former class includes R548, monitored since 1970, and G117–B15A, whose 215 s pulsation period has been monitored since 1974, and which is considered to be the ‘most stable optical clock known’. Córscico et al. (2013) derived $\dot{G}/G \leq -1.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for G117–B15A, and $\dot{G}/G \leq -1.3 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in the case of R548.

Estimates of the period change must account for each object's *proper motion*, which is where Gaia can contribute. For G117–B15A, Kepler et al. (2005) used the value known at the time to convert the observed rate, $\dot{P} = (4.27 \pm 0.80) \times 10^{-15} \text{ s s}^{-1}$, to the ‘true’ value, $\dot{P} = (3.57 \pm 0.82) \times 10^{-15} \text{ s s}^{-1}$. Improved estimates, based on the Gaia DR2 parallax ($\pi = 17.386 \pm 0.080 \text{ mas}$, $d = 57.5 \pm 0.2 \text{ pc}$) and proper motion ($-145.30 \pm 0.10, 0.006 \pm 0.088 \text{ mas/yr}$), were given by Kepler et al. (2021).

I EXPECT that Gaia will contribute further in these areas, and perhaps in at least three others:

(a) For the binary pulsar PSR 1913+16, the value of $\dot{G}/G \leq -(1.10 \pm 1.07) \times 10^{-11} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ was derived from measurement of the orbit decay compared with the predictions of general relativity (Damour et al. 1988). The ratio of the observed to predicted rate of decay, 0.997 ± 0.002 , was dominated by poorly known Galactic constants, specifically the Sun's distance from the Galactic centre, and the pulsar's proper motion and its distance from Earth (Weisberg & Taylor, 2005; Weisberg & Huang, 2016).

(b) The limit $\dot{G}/G \leq (0.2 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-11} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ from ranging of the Viking lander (Hellings et al., 1983) was limited by knowledge of the masses of the minor planets.

(c) A measurement of G in the Large Magellanic Cloud was based on 6 Cepheid variables in detached eclipsing binaries by Desmond et al. (2021). Again, improved Gaia astrometry and photometry should assist further.

FINALLY, with theoretical models for white dwarfs predicting that the period change is directly related to the rate of cooling, it follows that any additional source or sink of energy also modifies the rate of cooling and, hence, the rate of change of period.

Similar measurement programmes for white dwarfs are therefore also being used to place upper limits on the properties of (amongst others) axions (Isern et al. 1992; Córscico et al. 2012; Straniero et al. 2020; Di Luzio et al. 2022), and neutrinos (Blinnikov & Dunina-Barkovskaya 1994; Capozzi et al. 2020).